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ABSTRACT

We denote the set of first n natural numbers by $[1, n]$. We denote the set consisting of all r – subsets of $[1, n]$ by X_r^n , where r is an integer such that $0 < r \leq n$. The set consisting of all nonempty subsets of $[1, n]$ is denoted by X^n . The symmetric group S_n acts on sets X_r^n and X^n in natural way as $\pi(\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_r\}) = \{\pi(x_1), \pi(x_2), \dots, \pi(x_r)\}$. Let $\mathbb{C}X_r^n$ and $\mathbb{C}X^n$ denote the permutation modules associated with X_r^n and X^n respectively. In this paper, we decompose $\mathbb{C}X_r^n$ and $\mathbb{C}X^n$ upto equivalence for $n = 3, 4, 5$ and we obtain general rule for decomposition of $\mathbb{C}X_r^n$ and $\mathbb{C}X^n$ upto equivalence as a direct sum of Specht modules S^λ 's when n is even and when n is odd. By computing dimensions on both sides of these decompositions, we get some nice combinatorial identities.

Keywords: Permutation Representation, Irreducible Representations, Specht Modules, Character Tables.

MSC2020 Classification: 05A19, 20C15, 20C30.

1. INTRODUCTION

A representation expresses an abstract algebraic object in terms of matrices. The theory of matrices and linear operators is generally understood, therefore representing more abstract concepts in terms of well-known linear algebra objects can be useful for learning properties and occasionally for simplifying computations on more complex theories. The benefit of representation theory is that it transforms abstract algebraic issues into linear algebraic issues, which is a well-known field. Furthermore, representation theory is crucial to physics because it helps for explaining how a physical system's symmetry group impacts how its corresponding equations are solved. All areas of mathematics use representation theory to some extent.

In representation theory, group operations on vector spaces are of particular emphasis. However, groups operating on other groups or sets are also taken into account. Additionally, just consider vector spaces over fields with characteristic zero. A theory that applies to one specific algebraically closed field of characteristic zero also applies to all other algebraically closed fields of characteristic zero since the theory of algebraically closed fields of characteristic zero is complete.

The representation theory is a very active area of research. Recently, [Pogorelsky B. and Vay C., 2018] classified the extensions of simple Drinfeld double of FK3 modules and showed that it is of wild representation type. [Bauer U et al. 2020] gave a full classification of representation types of the subcategories of representations of an $m \times n$ rectangular grid with monomorphisms in one or both directions. [Sam S.V. and Snowden A., 2022] studied representation theory of triangular categories recently. [D'Adderio M. et al., 2022] studied Partial and global representations of finite groups. [Brundan J. and Vargas M., 2022] currently gave a new approach to the representation theory of the partition category.

The main contributions in this study are as follows:

- ✓ We decompose the permutation modules X_r^n and X^n into direct sum of irreducible representations of S_n . By computing dimensions on both sides of this decomposition, we get combinatorial identities.
- ✓ The content of the paper is structured as follows: section 2 contains some important results in general representation theory of groups, section 3 provides character tables of Symmetric groups, section 4 contains new results and discussion; finally, section 5 contains conclusions.

2. IMPORTANT RESULTS IN GENERAL REPRESENTATION THEORY OF GROUPS

In this section, we give some important results in Representation Theory of groups.

1. *Maschke's Theorem:* Let G be a finite group and let $V \neq \{0\}$ be a G -module. Then $V = W^{(1)} \oplus W^{(2)} \oplus \dots \oplus W^{(m)}$ where each $W^{(i)}$ is an irreducible G -submodule of V for $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$. i.e. any nonzero G -module is completely reducible.

2. Suppose $\phi^{(1)}, \dots, \phi^{(s)}$ is a complete list of inequivalent irreducible representations of G and suppose $\rho \sim m_1\phi^{(1)} \oplus m_2\phi^{(2)} \oplus \dots \oplus m_s\phi^{(s)}$. Then $m_i = (\chi_{\phi^{(i)}}, \chi_\rho)$ is the multiplicity of $\phi^{(i)}$ in ρ which is uniquely determined upto equivalence by its character.

3. Let (ρ, V) be a representation of group G with character χ_ρ , then (ρ, V) is irreducible representation iff $(\chi_\rho, \chi_\rho) = 1$.

4. The number of inequivalent irreducible representations of G is equal to the number of conjugacy classes of G .

5. The Specht modules S^μ for $\mu \vdash n$ form a complete list of inequivalent irreducible representations of S_n .

6. For any partition :

- (i) $\{e_t : t \text{ is a standard } \mu\text{-tableau}\}$ is a basis for S^μ .
- (ii) $\dim(S^\mu) = f^\mu = \text{number of standard } \mu\text{-tableaux}$.
- (iii) $\sum_{\mu \vdash n} (f^\mu)^2 = n!$.

7. (Hook Formula [J.S. Frame and et.al, 1954]): If $\mu \vdash n$, then $f^\mu = \frac{n!}{\prod_{(i,j) \in \mu} h_{i,j}}$.

3. CHARACTER TABLES OF SYMMETRIC GROUPS

Character Tables of S_3, S_4 and S_5 are as shown in Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3 respectively.

Table 1. Character Table of S_3

Conjugacy Class Representative	(1)	(12)	(123)
Cycle Type	(1,1,1)	(2,1)	(3)
Number of Elements	1	3	2
$\chi_{S^{(3)}}$	1	1	1
$\chi_{S^{(2,1)}}$	2	0	-1
$\chi_{S^{(1,1,1)}}$	1	-1	1

Table 2. Character Table of S_4

Conjugacy Class Representative	(1)	(12)	(12)(34)	(123)	(1234)
Cycle Type	(1,1,1,1)	(2,1,1)	(2,2)	(3,1)	(4)
No. of Elements	1	6	3	8	6
$\chi_{S^{(4)}}$	1	1	1	1	1
$\chi_{S^{(3,1)}}$	3	1	-1	0	-1
$\chi_{S^{(2,2)}}$	2	0	2	-1	0
$\chi_{S^{(2,1,1)}}$	3	-1	-1	0	1
$\chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1)}}$	1	-1	1	1	-1

Table 3. Character Table of S_5

Conjugacy Class Representative	(1)	(12)	(123)	(12)(34)	(1234)	(123)(45)	(12345)
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Cycle Type	(1,1,1,1,1)	(2,1,1,1)	(3,1,1)	(2,2,1)	(4,1)	(3,2)	(5)
No.of Elements	1	10	20	15	30	20	24
$\chi_{S^{(5)}}$	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
$\chi_{S^{(4,1)}}$	4	2	1	0	0	-1	-1
$\chi_{S^{(3,2)}}$	5	1	-1	1	-1	1	0
$\chi_{S^{(3,1,1)}}$	6	0	0	-2	0	0	1
$\chi_{S^{(2,2,1)}}$	5	-1	-1	1	1	-1	0
$\chi_{S^{(2,1,1,1)}}$	4	-2	1	0	0	1	-1
$\chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1,1)}}$	1	-1	1	1	-1	-1	1

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we obtain some results regarding the decomposition of permutation modules associated with X_r^n and X^n where X_r^n denotes the set consisting of all r -subsets of $[1, n]$ ($0 < r \leq n$) and X^n denotes the set consisting of all nonempty subsets of $[1, n]$ with action of S_n considered in natural way as $\pi(\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_r\}) = \{\pi(x_1), \pi(x_2), \dots, \pi(x_r)\}$.

Result 1: (i) $\mathbb{C}X_1^3 = S^{(3)} \oplus S^{(2,1)}$ (ii) $\mathbb{C}X_2^3 = S^{(3)} \oplus S^{(2,1)}$ (iii) $\mathbb{C}X_3^3 = S^{(3)}$ (iv) $\mathbb{C}X^3 = 3S^{(3)} \oplus 2S^{(2,1)}$

Proof: We write $S_3 = \{(1), (12), (13), (23), (123), (132)\}$

(i) Let $\mathbb{C}X_1^3 = \{c_1\{\mathbf{1}\} + c_2\{\mathbf{2}\} + c_3\{\mathbf{3}\} : c_i \in \mathbb{C}\}$. Let $\beta_1 = \{\{\mathbf{1}\}, \{\mathbf{2}\}, \{\mathbf{3}\}\}$ be standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X_1^3$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^3}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module associated with set X_1^3 . Let $\mathbb{C}X_2^3 = \{c_1\{\mathbf{1, 2}\} + c_2\{\mathbf{1, 3}\} + c_3\{\mathbf{2, 3}\} : c_i \in \mathbb{C}\}$. Let $\beta_2 = \{\{\mathbf{1, 2}\}, \{\mathbf{1, 3}\}, \{\mathbf{2, 3}\}\}$ be standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X_2^3$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^3}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module $\mathbb{C}X_2^3$. Let $\mathbb{C}X_3^3 = \{c\{\mathbf{1, 2, 3}\} : c \in \mathbb{C}\}$. Let $\beta_3 = \{\{\mathbf{1, 2, 3}\}\}$ be standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X_3^3$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^3}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module associated with set X_3^3 . Let $\mathbb{C}X^3 = \{c_1\{\mathbf{1}\} + c_2\{\mathbf{2}\} + c_3\{\mathbf{3}\} + c_4\{\mathbf{1, 2}\} + c_5\{\mathbf{1, 3}\} + c_6\{\mathbf{2, 3}\} + c_7\{\mathbf{1, 2, 3}\} = \mathbb{C}X_1^3 \oplus \mathbb{C}X_2^3 \oplus \mathbb{C}X_3^3$. Let $\beta = \beta_1 \cup \beta_2 \cup \beta_3$ be the standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X^3$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^3}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module associated with set $\mathbb{C}X^3$.

The following table 4 gives characters of modules $\mathbb{C}X_1^3, \mathbb{C}X_2^3, \mathbb{C}X_3^3$ and $\mathbb{C}X^3$.

Table 4: Characters for $\mathbb{C}X_1^3, \mathbb{C}X_2^3, \mathbb{C}X_3^3$ and $\mathbb{C}X^3$

Conjugacy Class Representative	(1)	(12)	(123)
Cycle Type	(1,1,1)	(2,1)	(3)
Number of Elements	1	3	2
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^3}$	3	1	0
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^3}$	3	1	0
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^3}$	1	1	1
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^3}$	7	3	1

From Table 1 and Table 4, we calculate multiplicities of Specht modules in above modules.

$$(i) \quad (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^3}, \chi_{S^{(3)}}) = \frac{1}{6}(1.3.1 + 3.1.1 + 2.0.1) = \frac{6}{6} = 1$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^3}, \chi_{S^{(2,1)}}) = \frac{1}{6}(1.3.2 + 3.1.0 + 2.0.(-1)) = \frac{6}{6} = 1$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^3}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{6}(1.3.1 + 3.1.(-1) + 2.0.1) = \frac{0}{6} = 0$$

Hence, $\mathbb{C}X_1^3 = S^{(3)} \oplus S^{(2,1)}$.

$$(ii) \quad (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^3}, \chi_{S^{(3)}}) = \frac{1}{6}(1.3.1 + 3.1.1 + 2.0.1) = \frac{6}{6} = 1$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^3}, \chi_{S^{(2,1)}}) = \frac{1}{6}(1.3.2 + 3.1.0 + 2.0.(-1)) = \frac{6}{6} = 1$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^3}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{6}(1.3.1 + 3.1.(-1) + 2.0.1) = \frac{0}{6} = 0$$

Hence, $\mathbb{C}X_2^3 = S^{(3)} \oplus S^{(2,1)}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(iii)} \quad (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^3}, \chi_{S^{(3)}}) &= \frac{1}{6}(1.1.1 + 3.1.1 + 2.1.1) = \frac{6}{6} = 1 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^3}, \chi_{S^{(2,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{6}(1.1.2 + 3.1.0 + 2.1.(-1)) = \frac{0}{6} = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^3}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{6}(1.1.1 + 3.1.(-1) + 2.1.1) = \frac{0}{6} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\mathbb{C}X_3^3 = S^{(3)}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(iv)} \quad (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^3}, \chi_{S^{(3)}}) &= \frac{1}{6}(1.7.1 + 3.3.1 + 2.1.1) = \frac{18}{6} = 3 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^3}, \chi_{S^{(2,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{6}(1.7.2 + 3.3.0 + 2.1.(-1)) = \frac{12}{6} = 2 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^3}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{6}(1.7.1 + 3.3.(-1) + 2.1.1) = \frac{0}{6} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\mathbb{C}X^3 = 3S^{(3)} \oplus 2S^{(2,1)}$.

Result 2: (i) $\mathbb{C}X_1^4 = S^{(4)} \oplus S^{(3,1)}$ (ii) $\mathbb{C}X_2^4 = S^{(4)} \oplus S^{(3,1)} \oplus S^{(2,2)}$ (iii) $\mathbb{C}X_3^4 = S^{(4)} \oplus S^{(3,1)}$ (iv) $\mathbb{C}X_4^4 = S^{(4)}$ (v) $\mathbb{C}X^4 = 4S^{(4)} \oplus 3S^{(3,1)} \oplus S^{(2,2)}$

Proof: Let $\mathbb{C}X_1^4 = \{c_1\{\mathbf{1}\} + c_2\{\mathbf{2}\} + c_3\{\mathbf{3}\} + c_4\{\mathbf{4}\} : c_i \in \mathbb{C}\}$. Let $\beta_1 = \{\{\mathbf{1}\}, \{\mathbf{2}\}, \{\mathbf{3}\}, \{\mathbf{4}\}\}$ be standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X_1^4$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^4}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module associated with set X_1^4 . Let $\mathbb{C}X_2^4 = \{c_1\{\mathbf{1,2}\} + c_2\{\mathbf{1,3}\} + c_3\{\mathbf{1,4}\} + c_4\{\mathbf{2,3}\} + c_5\{\mathbf{2,4}\} + c_6\{\mathbf{3,4}\} : c_i \in \mathbb{C}\}$. Let $\beta_2 = \{\{\mathbf{1,2}\}, \{\mathbf{1,3}\}, \{\mathbf{1,4}\}, \{\mathbf{2,3}\}, \{\mathbf{2,4}\}, \{\mathbf{3,4}\}\}$ be standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X_2^4$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^4}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module $\mathbb{C}X_2^4$. Let $\mathbb{C}X_3^4 = \{c_1\{\mathbf{1,2,3}\} + c_2\{\mathbf{1,2,4}\} + c_3\{\mathbf{1,3,4}\} + c_4\{\mathbf{2,3,4}\} : c_i \in \mathbb{C}\}$. Let $\beta_3 = \{\{\mathbf{1,2,3}\}, \{\mathbf{1,2,4}\}, \{\mathbf{1,3,4}\}, \{\mathbf{2,3,4}\}\}$ be standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X_3^4$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^4}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module associated with set X_3^4 . Let $\mathbb{C}X_4^4 = \{c\{\mathbf{1,2,3,4}\} : c \in \mathbb{C}\}$. Let $\beta_4 = \{\{\mathbf{1,2,3,4}\}\}$ be standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X_4^4$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^4}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module associated with set X_4^4 . Let $\mathbb{C}X^4 = \{c_1\{\mathbf{1}\} + c_2\{\mathbf{2}\} + c_3\{\mathbf{3}\} + c_4\{\mathbf{4}\} + c_5\{\mathbf{1,2}\} + c_6\{\mathbf{1,3}\} + c_7\{\mathbf{1,4}\} + c_8\{\mathbf{2,3}\} + c_9\{\mathbf{2,4}\} + c_{10}\{\mathbf{3,4}\} + c_{11}\{\mathbf{1,2,3}\} + c_{12}\{\mathbf{1,2,4}\} + c_{13}\{\mathbf{1,3,4}\} + c_{14}\{\mathbf{2,3,4}\} + c_{15}\{\mathbf{1,2,3,4}\} = \mathbb{C}X_1^4 \oplus \mathbb{C}X_2^4 \oplus \mathbb{C}X_3^4 \oplus \mathbb{C}X_4^4$. Let $\beta = \beta_1 \cup \beta_2 \cup \beta_3 \cup \beta_4$ be the standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X^4$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^4}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module associated with set $\mathbb{C}X^4$. The following table 5 gives characters of modules $\mathbb{C}X_1^4, \mathbb{C}X_2^4, \mathbb{C}X_3^4, \mathbb{C}X_4^4$ and $\mathbb{C}X^4$.

Table 5: Characters for $\mathbb{C}X_1^4, \mathbb{C}X_2^4, \mathbb{C}X_3^4, \mathbb{C}X_4^4$ and $\mathbb{C}X^4$

Conjugacy Class	(1)	(12)	(12)(34)	(123)	(1234)
Representative	(1,1,1,1)	(2,1,1)	(2,2)	(3,1)	(4)
Cycle Type	(1,1,1,1)	(2,1,1)	(2,2)	(3,1)	(4)
No. of Elements	1	6	3	8	6
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^4}$	4	2	0	1	0
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^4}$	6	2	2	0	0
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^4}$	4	2	0	1	0
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^4}$	1	1	1	1	1
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^4}$	15	7	3	3	1

From Table 2 and Table 5, we calculate multiplicities of Specht modules in above modules.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{(i)} \quad (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^4}, \chi_{S^{(4)}}) &= \frac{1}{24}(1.4.1 + 6.2.1 + 3.0.1 + 8.1.1 + 6.0.1) = \frac{24}{24} = 1 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^4}, \chi_{S^{(3,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{24}(1.4.3 + 6.2.1 + 3.0.(-1) + 8.1.0 + 6.0.(-1)) = \frac{24}{24} = 1 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^4}, \chi_{S^{(2,2)}}) &= \frac{1}{24}(1.4.2 + 6.2.0 + 3.0.2 + 8.1.(-1) + 6.0.0) = \frac{0}{24} = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^4}, \chi_{S^{(2,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{24}(1.4.3 + 6.2.(-1) + 3.0.(-1) + 8.1.0 + 6.0.1) = \frac{0}{24} = 0 \end{aligned}$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^4}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.4.1 + 6.2. (-1) + 3.0.1 + 8.1.1 + 6.0. (-1)) = \frac{0}{24} = 0$$

Hence) $\mathbb{C}X_1^4 = S^{(4)} \oplus S^{(3,1)}$

(ii)

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^4}, \chi_{S^{(4)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.6.1 + 6.2.1 + 3.2.1 + 8.0.1 + 6.0.1) = \frac{24}{24} = 1$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^4}, \chi_{S^{(3,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.6.3 + 6.2.1 + 3.2. (-1) + 8.0.0 + 6.0. (-1)) = \frac{24}{24} = 1$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^4}, \chi_{S^{(2,2)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.6.2 + 6.2.0 + 3.2.2 + 8.0. (-1) + 6.0.0) = \frac{24}{24} = 1$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^4}, \chi_{S^{(2,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.6.3 + 6.2. (-1) + 3.2. (-1) + 8.0.0 + 6.0.1) = \frac{0}{24} = 0$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^4}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.6.1 + 6.2. (-1) + 3.2.1 + 8.0.1 + 6.0. (-1)) = \frac{0}{24} = 0$$

Hence, $\mathbb{C}X_2^4 = S^{(4)} \oplus S^{(3,1)} \oplus S^{(2,2)}$

(iii)

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^4}, \chi_{S^{(4)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.4.1 + 6.2.1 + 3.0.1 + 8.1.1 + 6.0.1) = \frac{24}{24} = 1$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^4}, \chi_{S^{(3,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.4.3 + 6.2.1 + 3.0. (-1) + 8.1.0 + 6.0. (-1)) = \frac{24}{24} = 1$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^4}, \chi_{S^{(2,2)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.4.2 + 6.2.0 + 3.0.2 + 8.1. (-1) + 6.0.0) = \frac{0}{24} = 0$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^4}, \chi_{S^{(2,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.4.3 + 6.2. (-1) + 3.0. (-1) + 8.1.0 + 6.0.1) = \frac{0}{24} = 0$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^4}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.4.1 + 6.2. (-1) + 3.0.1 + 8.1.1 + 6.0. (-1)) = \frac{0}{24} = 0$$

Hence, $\mathbb{C}X_3^4 = S^{(4)} \oplus S^{(3,1)}$

(iv)

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^4}, \chi_{S^{(4)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.1.1 + 6.1.1 + 3.1.1 + 8.1.1 + 6.1.1) = \frac{24}{24} = 1$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^4}, \chi_{S^{(3,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.1.3 + 6.1.1 + 3.1. (-1) + 8.1.0 + 6.1. (-1)) = \frac{0}{24} = 0$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^4}, \chi_{S^{(2,2)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.1.2 + 6.1.0 + 3.1.2 + 8.1. (-1) + 6.1.0) = \frac{0}{24} = 0$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^4}, \chi_{S^{(2,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.1.3 + 6.1. (-1) + 3.1. (-1) + 8.1.0 + 6.1.1) = \frac{0}{24} = 0$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^4}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.1.1 + 6.1. (-1) + 3.1.1 + 8.1.1 + 6.1. (-1)) = \frac{0}{24} = 0$$

Hence, $\mathbb{C}X_4^4 = S^{(4)}$

(v)

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^4}, \chi_{S^{(4)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.15.1 + 6.7.1 + 3.3.1 + 8.3.1 + 6.1.1) = \frac{96}{24} = 4$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^4}, \chi_{S^{(3,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.15.3 + 6.7.1 + 3.3. (-1) + 8.3.0 + 6.1. (-1)) = \frac{72}{24} = 3$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^4}, \chi_{S^{(2,2)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.15.2 + 6.7.0 + 3.3.2 + 8.3. (-1) + 6.1.0) = \frac{24}{24} = 1$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^4}, \chi_{S^{(2,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.15.3 + 6.7. (-1) + 3.3. (-1) + 8.3.0 + 6.1.1) = \frac{0}{24} = 0$$

$$(\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^4}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{24} (1.15.1 + 6.7. (-1) + 3.3.1 + 8.3.1 + 6.1. (-1)) = \frac{0}{24} = 0$$

Hence, $\mathbb{C}X_4^4 = 4S^{(4)} \oplus 3S^{(3,1)} \oplus S^{(2,2)}$

Result 3: (i) $\mathbb{C}X_1^5 = S^{(5)} \oplus S^{(4,1)}$, (ii) $\mathbb{C}X_2^5 = S^{(5)} \oplus S^{(4,1)} \oplus S^{(3,2)}$, (iii) $\mathbb{C}X_3^5 = S^{(5)} \oplus S^{(4,1)} \oplus S^{(3,2)}$

(iv) $\mathbb{C}X_4^5 = S^{(5)} \oplus S^{(4,1)}$, (v) $\mathbb{C}X_5^5 = S^{(5)}$, (vi) $\mathbb{C}X^5 = 5S^{(5)} \oplus 4S^{(4,1)} \oplus 2S^{(3,2)}$.

Proof: Let $\mathbb{C}X_1^5 = \{c_1\{\mathbf{1}\} + c_2\{\mathbf{2}\} + c_3\{\mathbf{3}\} + c_4\{\mathbf{4}\} + c_5\{\mathbf{5}\}; c_i \in \mathbb{C}\}$. . Let $\beta_1 = \{\{\mathbf{1}\}, \{\mathbf{2}\}, \{\mathbf{3}\}, \{\mathbf{4}\}, \{\mathbf{5}\}\}$ be standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X_1^5$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^5}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module associated with set X_1^5 . Let $\mathbb{C}X_2^5 = \{c_1\{\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{2}\} + c_2\{\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{3}\} + c_3\{\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{4}\} + c_4\{\mathbf{1}, \mathbf{5}\} + c_5\{\mathbf{2}, \mathbf{3}\} + c_6\{\mathbf{2}, \mathbf{4}\} + c_7\{\mathbf{2}, \mathbf{5}\} + c_8\{\mathbf{3}, \mathbf{4}\} + c_9\{\mathbf{3}, \mathbf{5}\} + c_{10}\{\mathbf{4}, \mathbf{5}\}; c_i \in \mathbb{C}\}$.

Let $\beta_2 = \{\{1, 2\}, \{1, 3\}, \{1, 4\}, \{1, 5\}, \{2, 3\}, \{2, 4\}, \{2, 5\}, \{3, 4\}, \{3, 5\}, \{4, 5\}\}$ be standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X_2^5$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^5}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module $\mathbb{C}X_2^5$. Let $\mathbb{C}X_3^5 = \{c_1\{1, 2, 3\} + c_2\{1, 2, 4\} + c_3\{1, 2, 5\} + c_4\{1, 3, 4\} + c_5\{1, 3, 5\} + c_6\{1, 4, 5\} + c_7\{2, 3, 4\} + c_8\{2, 3, 5\} + c_9\{2, 4, 5\} + c_{10}\{3, 4, 5\}; c_i \in \mathbb{C}\}$.

Let $\beta_3 = \{\{1, 2, 3\}, \{1, 2, 4\}, \{1, 2, 5\}, \{1, 3, 4\}, \{1, 3, 5\}, \{1, 4, 5\}, \{2, 3, 4\}, \{2, 3, 5\}, \{2, 4, 5\}, \{3, 4, 5\}\}$ be standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X_3^5$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^5}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module associated with set X_3^5 .

Let $\mathbb{C}X_4^5 = \{c_1\{1, 2, 3, 4\} + c_2\{1, 2, 3, 5\} + c_3\{1, 3, 4, 5\} + c_4\{1, 2, 4, 5\} + c_5\{2, 3, 4, 5\}; c_i \in \mathbb{C}\}$. Let $\beta_4 = \{\{1, 2, 3, 4\}, \{1, 2, 3, 5\}, \{1, 3, 4, 5\}, \{1, 2, 4, 5\}, \{2, 3, 4, 5\}\}$ be standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X_4^5$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^5}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module associated with set X_4^5 .

Let $\mathbb{C}X_5^5 = \{c\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}; c \in \mathbb{C}\}$. Let $\beta_5 = \{\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}\}$ be standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X_5^5$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_5^5}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module associated with set X_5^5 .

Let $\mathbb{C}X^5 = \{c_1\{1\} + c_2\{2\} + c_3\{3\} + c_4\{4\} + c_5\{5\} + c_6\{1, 2\} + c_7\{1, 3\} + c_8\{1, 4\} + c_9\{1, 5\} + c_{10}\{2, 3\} + c_{11}\{2, 4\} + c_{12}\{2, 5\} + c_{13}\{3, 4\} + c_{14}\{3, 5\} + c_{15}\{4, 5\} + c_{16}\{1, 2, 3\} + c_{17}\{1, 2, 4\} + c_{18}\{1, 2, 5\} + c_{19}\{1, 3, 4\} + c_{20}\{1, 3, 5\} + c_{21}\{1, 4, 5\} + c_{22}\{2, 3, 4\} + c_{23}\{2, 3, 5\} + c_{24}\{2, 4, 5\} + c_{25}\{3, 4, 5\} + c_{26}\{1, 2, 3, 4\} + c_{27}\{1, 2, 3, 5\} + c_{28}\{1, 3, 4, 5\} + c_{29}\{1, 2, 4, 5\} + c_{30}\{2, 3, 4, 5\} + c_{31}\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\} = \mathbb{C}X_1^5 \oplus \mathbb{C}X_2^5 \oplus \mathbb{C}X_3^5 \oplus \mathbb{C}X_4^5 \oplus \mathbb{C}X_5^5$. Let $\beta = \beta_1 \cup \beta_2 \cup \beta_3 \cup \beta_4 \cup \beta_5$ be the standard basis for $\mathbb{C}X^5$. Let $\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^5}$ be the character of matrix representation corresponding to the permutation module associated with set $\mathbb{C}X^5$.

The following table 6 gives characters of modules $\mathbb{C}X_1^5, \mathbb{C}X_2^5, \mathbb{C}X_3^5, \mathbb{C}X_4^5, \mathbb{C}X_5^5$ and $\mathbb{C}X^5$.

Table 6: Characters for $\mathbb{C}X_1^5, \mathbb{C}X_2^5, \mathbb{C}X_3^5, \mathbb{C}X_4^5, \mathbb{C}X_5^5$ and $\mathbb{C}X^5$

Conjugacy Class Representative	(1)	(12)	(123)	(12)(34)	(1234)	(123)(45)	(12345)
Cycle Type	(1,1,1,1,1)	(2,1,1,1)	(3,1,1)	(2,2,1)	(4,1)	(3,2)	(5)
No. of Elements	1	10	20	15	30	20	24
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^5}$	5	3	2	1	1	0	0
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^5}$	10	4	1	2	0	1	0
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^5}$	10	4	1	2	0	1	0
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^5}$	5	3	2	1	1	0	0
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_5^5}$	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
$\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^5}$	31	15	7	7	3	3	1

From Table 3 and Table 6, we calculate multiplicities of Specht modules in above modules.

$$\begin{aligned}
 (i) \quad & (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^5}, \chi_{S^{(5)}}) = \frac{1}{120} (1.5.1 + 10.3.1 + 20.2.1 + 15.1.1 + 30.1.1 + 20.0.1 + 24.0.1) = \frac{120}{120} = 1 \\
 & (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^5}, \chi_{S^{(4,1)}}) = \frac{1}{120} (1.5.4 + 10.3.2 + 20.2.1 + 15.1.0 + 30.1.0 + 20.0.(-1) + 24.0.(-1)) = \frac{120}{120} = 1 \\
 & (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^5}, \chi_{S^{(3,2)}}) = \frac{1}{120} (1.5.5 + 10.3.1 + 20.2.(-1) + 15.1.1 + 30.1.(-1) + 20.0.1 + 24.0.0) = 0 \\
 & (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^5}, \chi_{S^{(3,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{120} (1.5.6 + 10.3.0 + 20.2.0 + 15.1.(-2) + 30.1.0 + 20.0.0 + 24.0.1) = 0 \\
 & (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^5}, \chi_{S^{(2,2,1)}}) = \frac{1}{120} (1.5.5 + 10.3.(-1) + 20.2.(-1) + 15.1.1 + 30.1.1 + 20.0.(-1) + 24.0.0) = 0 \\
 & (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^5}, \chi_{S^{(2,1,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{120} (1.5.4 + 10.3.(-2) + 20.2.1 + 15.1.0 + 30.1.0 + 20.0.1 + 24.0.(-1)) = 0 \\
 & (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_1^5}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1,1)}}) = \frac{1}{120} (1.5.1 + 10.3.(-1) + 20.2.1 + 15.1.1 + 30.1.(-1) + 20.0.(-1) + 24.0.1) = 0 \\
 \text{Hence, } & \mathbb{C}X_1^5 = S^{(5)} \oplus S^{(4,1)}. \\
 (ii) \quad & (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^5}, \chi_{S^{(5)}}) = \frac{1}{120} (1.10.1 + 10.4.1 + 20.1.1 + 15.2.1 + 30.0.1 + 20.1.1 + 24.0.1) = \frac{120}{120} = 1 \\
 & (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^5}, \chi_{S^{(4,1)}}) = \frac{1}{120} (1.10.4 + 10.4.2 + 20.1.1 + 15.2.0 + 30.0.0 + 20.1.(-1) + 24.0.(-1)) = \frac{120}{120} = 1 \\
 & (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^5}, \chi_{S^{(3,2)}}) = \frac{1}{120} (1.10.5 + 10.4.1 + 20.1.(-1) + 15.2.1 + 30.0.(-1) + 20.1.1 + 24.0.0) = \frac{120}{120} = 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^5}, \chi_{S^{(3,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.10.6 + 10.4.0 + 20.1.0 + 15.2.(-2) + 30.0.0 + 20.1.0 + 24.0.1) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^5}, \chi_{S^{(2,2,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.10.5 + 10.4.(-1) + 20.1.(-1) + 15.2.1 + 30.0.1 + 20.1.(-1) + 24.0.0) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^5}, \chi_{S^{(2,1,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.10.4 + 10.4.(-2) + 20.1.1 + 15.2.0 + 30.0.0 + 20.1.1 + 24.0.(-1)) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_2^5}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.10.1 + 10.4.(-1) + 20.1.1 + 15.2.1 + 30.0.(-1) + 20.1.(-1) + 24.0.1) = 0 \\ \text{Hence, } \mathbb{C}X_2^5 &= S^{(5)} \oplus S^{(4,1)} \oplus S^{(3,2)}. \\ \text{(iii) } (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^5}, \chi_{S^{(5)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.10.1 + 10.4.1 + 20.1.1 + 15.2.1 + 30.0.1 + 20.1.1 + 24.0.1) = \frac{120}{120} = 1 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^5}, \chi_{S^{(4,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.10.4 + 10.4.2 + 20.1.1 + 15.2.0 + 30.0.0 + 20.1.(-1) + 24.0.(-1)) = \frac{120}{120} = 1 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^5}, \chi_{S^{(3,2)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.10.5 + 10.4.1 + 20.1.(-1) + 15.2.1 + 30.0.(-1) + 20.1.1 + 24.0.0) = \frac{120}{120} = 1 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^5}, \chi_{S^{(3,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.10.6 + 10.4.0 + 20.1.0 + 15.2.(-2) + 30.0.0 + 20.1.0 + 24.0.1) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^5}, \chi_{S^{(2,2,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.10.5 + 10.4.(-1) + 20.1.(-1) + 15.2.1 + 30.0.1 + 20.1.(-1) + 24.0.0) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^5}, \chi_{S^{(2,1,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.10.4 + 10.4.(-2) + 20.1.1 + 15.2.0 + 30.0.0 + 20.1.1 + 24.0.(-1)) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_3^5}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.10.1 + 10.4.(-1) + 20.1.1 + 15.2.1 + 30.0.(-1) + 20.1.(-1) + 24.0.1) = 0 \\ \text{Hence, } \mathbb{C}X_3^5 &= S^{(5)} \oplus S^{(4,1)} \oplus S^{(3,2)}. \\ \text{(iv) } (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^5}, \chi_{S^{(5)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.5.1 + 10.3.1 + 20.2.1 + 15.1.1 + 30.1.1 + 20.0.1 + 24.0.1) = \frac{120}{120} = 1 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^5}, \chi_{S^{(4,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.5.4 + 10.3.2 + 20.2.1 + 15.1.0 + 30.1.0 + 20.0.(-1) + 24.0.(-1)) = \frac{120}{120} = 1 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^5}, \chi_{S^{(3,2)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.5.5 + 10.3.1 + 20.2.(-1) + 15.1.1 + 30.1.(-1) + 20.0.1 + 24.0.0) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^5}, \chi_{S^{(3,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.5.6 + 10.3.0 + 20.2.0 + 15.1.(-2) + 30.1.0 + 20.0.0 + 24.0.1) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^5}, \chi_{S^{(2,2,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.5.5 + 10.3.(-1) + 20.2.(-1) + 15.1.1 + 30.1.1 + 20.0.(-1) + 24.0.0) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^5}, \chi_{S^{(2,1,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.5.4 + 10.3.(-2) + 20.2.1 + 15.1.0 + 30.1.0 + 20.0.1 + 24.0.(-1)) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_4^5}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.5.1 + 10.3.(-1) + 20.2.1 + 15.1.1 + 30.1.(-1) + 20.0.(-1) + 24.0.1) = 0 \\ \text{Hence, } \mathbb{C}X_4^5 &= S^{(5)} \oplus S^{(4,1)}. \\ \text{(v) } (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_5^5}, \chi_{S^{(5)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.1.1 + 10.1.1 + 20.1.1 + 15.1.1 + 30.1.1 + 20.1.1 + 24.1.1) = \frac{120}{120} = 1 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_5^5}, \chi_{S^{(4,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.1.4 + 10.1.2 + 20.1.1 + 15.1.0 + 30.1.0 + 20.1.(-1) + 24.1.(-1)) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_5^5}, \chi_{S^{(3,2)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.1.5 + 10.1.1 + 20.1.(-1) + 15.1.1 + 30.1.(-1) + 20.1.1 + 24.1.0) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_5^5}, \chi_{S^{(3,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.1.6 + 10.1.0 + 20.1.0 + 15.1.(-2) + 30.1.0 + 20.1.0 + 24.1.1) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_5^5}, \chi_{S^{(2,2,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.1.5 + 10.1.(-1) + 20.1.(-1) + 15.1.1 + 30.1.1 + 20.1.(-1) + 24.1.0) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_5^5}, \chi_{S^{(2,1,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.1.4 + 10.1.(-2) + 20.1.1 + 15.1.0 + 30.1.0 + 20.1.1 + 24.1.(-1)) = 0 \\ (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X_5^5}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.1.1 + 10.1.(-1) + 20.1.1 + 15.1.1 + 30.1.(-1) + 20.1.(-1) + 24.1.1) = 0 \\ \text{Hence, } \mathbb{C}X_5^5 &= S^{(5)}. \\ \text{(vi) } (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^5}, \chi_{S^{(5)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.31.1 + 10.15.1 + 20.7.1 + 15.7.1 + 30.3.1 + 20.3.1 + 24.1.1) = \frac{600}{120} = 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^5}, \chi_{S^{(4,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.31.4 + 10.15.2 + 20.7.1 + 15.7.0 + 30.3.0 + 20.3.(-1) + 24.1.(-1)) = \frac{480}{120} \\
 &= 4 \\
 (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^5}, \chi_{S^{(3,2)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.31.5 + 10.15.1 + 20.7.(-1) + 15.7.1 + 30.3.(-1) + 20.3.1 + 24.1.0) = \frac{240}{120} = 2 \\
 (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^5}, \chi_{S^{(3,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.31.6 + 10.15.0 + 20.7.0 + 15.7.(-2) + 30.3.0 + 20.3.0 + 24.1.1) = 0 \\
 (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^5}, \chi_{S^{(2,2,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.31.5 + 10.15.(-1) + 20.7.(-1) + 15.7.1 + 30.3.1 + 20.3.(-1) + 24.1.0) = 0 \\
 (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^5}, \chi_{S^{(2,1,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.31.4 + 10.15.(-2) + 20.7.1 + 15.7.0 + 30.3.0 + 20.3.1 + 24.1.(-1)) = \frac{0}{120} \\
 &= 0 \\
 (\chi_{\mathbb{C}X^5}, \chi_{S^{(1,1,1,1,1)}}) &= \frac{1}{120} (1.31.1 + 10.15.(-1) + 20.7.1 + 15.7.1 + 30.3.(-1) + 20.3.(-1) + 24.1.1) = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\mathbb{C}X^5 = 5S^{(5)} \oplus 4S^{(4,1)} \oplus 2S^{(3,2)}$.

After manually decomposing the permutation modules corresponding to X^n as is done for $n = 3, 4, 5$ for $n = 6, 7, 8$ we found following result for general natural numbers $n \geq 3$ as follows:

(i) $\mathbb{C}X_r^n = S^{(n)} \oplus S^{(n-1,1)} \oplus \dots \oplus S^{(n-r,r)} \quad \forall 1 \leq r \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ denotes greatest integer function. If $r > \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$, then $1 \leq n-r \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and we get $\mathbb{C}X_r^n = \mathbb{C}X_{n-r}^n = S^{(n)} \oplus S^{(n-1,1)} \oplus \dots \oplus S^{(r,n-r)}$

(ii) $X^n = nS^{(n)} \oplus (n-1)S^{(n-1,1)} \oplus (n-3)S^{(n-2,2)} \oplus \dots \oplus 1S^{\binom{n}{2,2}}$ if n is even.

(iii) $X^n = nS^{(n)} \oplus (n-1)S^{(n-1,1)} \oplus (n-3)S^{(n-2,2)} \oplus \dots \oplus 2S^{\binom{n+1}{2}, \frac{n-1}{2}}$ if n is odd.

After computing dimensions on both sides, we get for $n \geq 3$

(i) $C(n, r) = f^{(n)} + f^{(n-1,1)} + \dots + f^{(n-r,r)} \quad \forall 1 \leq r \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$. If $r > \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$, then $1 \leq n-r \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and we get $C(n, n-r) = f^{(n)} + f^{(n-1,1)} + \dots + f^{(r,n-r)}$.

(ii) $2^n - 1 = nf^{(n)} + (n-1)f^{(n-1,1)} + (n-3)f^{(n-2,2)} + (n-5)f^{(n-3,3)} + \dots + 1f^{\binom{n}{2,2}}$ if n is even.

(iii) $2^n - 1 = nf^{(n)} + (n-1)f^{(n-1,1)} + (n-3)f^{(n-2,2)} + (n-5)f^{(n-3,3)} + \dots + 2f^{\binom{n+1}{2}, \frac{n-1}{2}}$ if n is odd.

5. CONCLUSIONS

If X^n is a S_n -set where $n \geq 3$, then the permutation module corresponding to X^n is a direct sum of Specht modules $S^{(n)}, S^{(n-1,1)}, S^{(n-2,2)}, \dots, S^{\binom{n}{2,2}}$ with multiplicities $n, n-1, n-3, n-5, \dots, 1$ respectively if n is even and X^n is a direct sum of Specht modules $S^{(n)}, S^{(n-1,1)}, S^{(n-2,2)}, \dots, S^{\binom{n+1}{2}, \frac{n-1}{2}}$ with multiplicities $n, n-1, n-3, n-5, \dots, 2$ respectively if n is odd.

For any natural number $n \geq 3$, following combinatorial identities hold

(i) $C(n, r) = f^{(n)} + f^{(n-1,1)} + \dots + f^{(n-r,r)} \quad \forall 1 \leq r \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$. If $r > \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$, then $1 \leq n-r \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and we get $C(n, n-r) = f^{(n)} + f^{(n-1,1)} + \dots + f^{(r,n-r)}$.

(i) $2^n - 1 = nf^{(n)} + (n-1)f^{(n-1,1)} + (n-3)f^{(n-2,2)} + (n-5)f^{(n-3,3)} + \dots + 1f^{\binom{n}{2,2}}$ if n is even.

(ii) $2^n - 1 = nf^{(n)} + (n-1)f^{(n-1,1)} + (n-3)f^{(n-2,2)} + (n-5)f^{(n-3,3)} + \dots + 2f^{\binom{n+1}{2}, \frac{n-1}{2}}$ if n is odd.

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